

Table S2: Percentage of synchronized, free-run and arrhythmic stridulation and locomotion behavior in male *Gryllus bimaculatus* adult crickets exposed to four different lifelong ALAN intensities.

Treatment	Stridulation (%)			Locomotion (%)		
	Synchronized	Free-run	Arrhythmic	Synchronized	Free-run	Arrhythmic
LD	86.67	13.33	0	100	0	0
LL₂	15	80	5	40	60	0
LL₅	15	80	5	29.41	47.06	23.53
LL	0	70.83	29.17	2.38	54.76	42.86